

THE IMPACT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ON ENHANCING SPEAKING SKILLS

Turdiyeva Shohida Yusuf qizi

3rd Faculty of Foreign Languages and Literature, UzSWLU

Scientific advisor: Mannonova Feruza Sherali qizi

Senior teacher of English faculty 3, Department of Integrated course of English Language, UzSWLU

Abstract: Today, artificial intelligence is developing significantly in different fields: especially, education and language learning. Artificial Intelligence is becoming an integral part of our lives. This article presents about the role of Artificial intelligence in developing speaking skills. Language learners can make progress in learning languages due to the opportunities of AI.

Keywords: language learning, speaking skills, Elsa speak, technologies, Duolingo, Artificial intelligence (AI), Artificial intelligence technologies.

Annotatsiya: Bugungi kunda sun'iy intellekt turli sohalarda sezilarli darajada rivojlanmoqda: ayniqsa, ta'lim va til o'rganish. Sun'iy intellekt hayotimizning ajralmas qismiga aylanib bormoqda. Ushbu maqolada sun'iy intellektning nutq ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishdagi o'rni haqida so'z boradi. Til o'rganuvchilar AI imkoniyatlari tufayli tillarni o'rganishda muvaffaqiyatga erishishlari mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: til o'rganish, nutq qobiliyatlari, Elza gapirish, texnologiyalar, Duolingo, Sun'iy intellekt, Sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalari.

Аннотация: Сегодня искусственный интеллект добивается значительных успехов в различных областях: особенно в образовании и изучении языков. Искусственный интеллект становится неотъемлемой частью нашей жизни. В данной статье обсуждается роль искусственного интеллекта в развитии навыков говорения. Изучающие языки могут добиться успеха в изучении языков благодаря возможностям ИИ.

Ключевые слова: изучение языка, навыки говорения, Elsa speak, технологии, Duolingo, искусственный интеллект (ИИ), Технологии искусственного интеллекта.

Introduction: Nowadays Artificial intelligence technologies are making significant advancements in the field of education. Language learning is easy and effective with the help of AI. Educators can improve pronunciation and accuracy in their speaking skills. AI tools explore a learner's performance, weak sides and strengths for making customized lessons for them. Language learners can learn a language well, effectively and quickly with the following tools. They are Duolingo and Elsa speak. Duolingo utilize AI for customizing lessons based on

the learner's growth and performance. This tool consists of speaking tasks. Learners can speak and get real-time feedback on their fluency with this app. As a result, educators can be aware their mistakes and they will try to correct them. This way, their speaking skills will develop. Another one is Elsa speak (English Language Speech Assistant) is an AI-based app that is useful, effective and related to pronunciation practice. It is effective for speaking English more clearly and confidently. These apps are interesting and language learners can learn a language in a fun way with them. They also help boost confidence. Educators can practice any time, anywhere with the help of these apps and of course they can use their smartphones, smart watches and other digital tools. One of the opportunities for learning foreign languages is the productiveness of chatbots and virtual assistants in communicative practice. These systems suggest educators the chance to interact in like real surroundings. As a result, these systems contribute to the improvement of learners' confidence and fluency.

In conclusion, today we have a lot of opportunities for learning languages thanks of Artificial intelligence. AI systems can progress speaking skills in learning other foreign languages. AI is important for improving speaking skills, it suggests understandable, effective and customized language learning background and it helps you develop fluency and accuracy in speaking by analyzing your mistakes.

References:

1. <https://talkpal.ai/the-role-of-ai-in-developing-speaking-skills/>
2. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/381597137_The_Potential_of_Artificial_Intelligence_to_Improve_Speaking_Skills_in_a_Second_Language_English_Fluently